

RP-KIGALI COLLEGE

ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONICS ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

IOT BASED SMART NOTICE BOARD FOR INFORMATION SHARING IN RP -KIGALI COLLEGE

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Advanced Diploma in Electronics and Telecommunication Technology

By: TUYISHIME Emmanuel 21RP06943

ISHIMWE Shalom 21RP01543

Supervised by: GASANA James Madson

NTIRANTA Jean Claude

Kigali, October 2024

DECLARATION

We do hereby declare that this Project submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the Advanced Diploma in Electronics and Telecommunication Technology, at RP-Kigali College, is our original work and has not previously been submitted elsewhere. Also, we do declare that a complete list of references is provided indicating all the sources of information quoted or cited.

Name: TUYISHIME Emmanuel

Signature:

Name: ISHIMWE Shalom

Signature:

APPROVAL SHEET

I confirm that the work reported in this project was carried out by the candidates under my supervision and it has been submitted with my approval as the RP-Kigali College supervisor.

Project supervisor's name:

GASANA James Madson

Signature:

Date:

NTIRANTA Jean Claude

Signature:

Date:

Head of Department's name:

GASANA James Madson

Signature:

Date:

DEDICATION

We dedicate this project to:

- ✓ All staff members, lecturers of RP-Kigali College, especially our supervisors.
- ✓ Our lovely parents
- ✓ Our beloved brother and sisters
- ✓ Our marvelous classmates
- ✓ Our friends

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

With a deep sense and profound gratitude, we take this opportunity to convey our sincere thanks to Almighty God for the good health and wellbeing that were necessary to complete this research project. We are blessed by His grace and blessings through our lives.

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Without their knowledge and assistance this work would not have been successful. Our heartfelt thanks and unreserved recognition are addressed to our supervisor GASANA James Madson and NTIRANTA Jean Claude who despite multitudes of daily task and multiple responsibilities, accepted to support and guide this work. Their guidance, courage, insight, patience and support played an important role to the fulfillment of this work.

ABSTRACT

This project titled "IOT-BASED SMART NOTICE BOARD FOR INFORMATION SHARING IN RP KIGALI COLLEGE," aims to improve the campus' communication by displaying notices on a TV screen connected to a Raspberry Pi. The system allows authorized users to upload notices via a web dashboard, with access controlled through a secure login page. A key feature includes an ultrasonic sensor that detects and records the number of people approaching the notice board, with this data transmitted to a database and displayed on the web dashboard. This study addresses the challenge of effective, real-time information sharing in public spaces while tracking engagement.

The objectives are to improve communication, ensure timely notice updates, and provide feedback on notice board usage. Practically, the project integrates IoT technologies such as Raspberry Pi, sensors, and cloud-based data handling. The findings will highlight improvements in notice management and user engagement. The system's significance lies in its ability to enhance accessibility and real-time interaction with the notice board. Recommendations suggest to expand the system's scalability and adding features like notification indicators and power backup.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	i
APPROVAL SHEET	ii
DEDICATION	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iv
ABSTRACT	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
LIST OF FIGURES.....	viii
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	x
DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS.....	xi
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 Introduction	1
1.1 Background of the project	1
1.2 Problem statement	2
1.3 Purpose of the study	2
1.4 Project objectives.....	2
1.4.1 General objectives	2
1.4.2 Specific objectives.....	3
1.5 Research questions	3
1.6 Scope of the project	4
1.7 Methodology and Technics	4
1.8 Delimitation	5
1.9 Organization of the project	5
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.0 Introduction	6
2.1 Concepts, Opinions, Ideas from Authors/Experts	6
2.2 Related study	6
CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY.....	9
3.0 Introduction	9
3.1 Research design	9

3.2	Research population	9
3.3	Sample size	10
3.4	Research instrument	10
3.4.1	Choice of the research instrument.....	10
3.4.2	Validity and Reliability of the Instrument.....	11
3.5	Data gathering procedures	11
3.6	Limitation of the study	11
CHAPTER FOUR: PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS		12
4.0	Introduction	12
4.1	Calculations	12
4.2	Drawings.....	12
4.2.1	Block diagram of the project.....	12
4.2.2	Working principle of the project	13
4.2.3	Flowchart.....	13
4.2.4	Circuit diagram.....	14
4.3	Specifications.....	15
4.3.1	Main components Used.....	15
4.4	Cost estimation	18
4.4.1	Project plan.....	18
4.5	Implementation.....	20
4.5.1	Log in page.....	20
4.5.2	Dashboard.....	20
4.5.3	Notice database	21
4.5.4	Sensor database	22
CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS		23
5.0	Introduction	23
5.1	Conclusion	23
5.2	Recommendations	23
5.3	Suggestion for further study	24
REFERENCES.....		25
APPENDIX.....		27

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 2</i> Block diagram	12
<i>Figure 3</i> Flowchart	13
<i>Figure 4</i> Circuit diagram	14
<i>Figure 5</i> NodeMCU	15
<i>Figure 6</i> Ultrasonic	16
<i>Figure 7</i> Jumper wires	16
<i>Figure 8</i> PCB	17
<i>Figure 9</i> Raspberry Pi 4b	18
<i>Figure 10</i> Log in Page	20
<i>Figure 11</i> Dashboard	20
<i>Figure 12</i> Database	21
<i>Figure 13</i> Sensor Database	22
<i>Figure 14</i> Sensor circuit	27
<i>Figure 15</i> notice display	27
<i>Figure 16</i> Arduino IDE Code	30

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Organization of the project 5
Table 2 Cost Estimation 18

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ESP: Espressif Systems Programmable

GPIO: General purpose input output

IoT: Internet of things

NODEMCU: Node Micro-Controller Unit

PC: Personal Computer

RP: Rwanda Polytechnic

WI-FI: Wireless Fidelity

DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS

Database: Is an organized collection of data that is stored and managed on a computer system.

in real time.

Real-time tracking: Tracking that provides updates on the location of a vehicle or good

Smart notice board: Is a digital display system that uses technology, such as IoT, to present information or announcements in real time.

Web-based dashboard: Is an online tool that shows important information in an easy-to-read format.

It helps users track data and manage tasks from any device with internet access

Web-based interface: Is a user-friendly platform that allows people to interact with software or systems through a web browser.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

Traditional methods of delivering information at RP-Kigali College, such as paper notice boards, are outdated, labor-intensive, and inefficient. The proposed solution is an IoT-based smart notice board system that enables real-time, remote management of information displays. Utilizing a web-based interface, authorized users can update content from any location, while the Raspberry Pi will serve as the receiver for the TV screen, enabling Wi-Fi access, as the sensor transmits data to the database through the NodeMCU, which manages the wireless connection. This system supports the display of text, images, and documents, making it versatile and user-friendly. By adopting this technology RP-Kigali College can significantly improve communication efficiency, ensure timely information dissemination, and enhance overall engagement within the institution

1.1 Background of the project

According to a study by Chauhan and Sharma (2020), traditional paper-based notice boards in public areas are inefficient, labor-intensive, and fail to provide timely updates. To address these issues with the advancement in technology, the 'IoT-based smart notice board' project implementation introduces a modern solution using Internet of Things (IoT) technology for real-time and remote management of information. A web-based interface allows authorized users to update content from any location, while an ultrasonic sensor tells the administrator the number of events before the notice board on the dashboard through NodeMCU providing the Wi-Fi connection. Supporting text, images, and documents, this system improves communication efficiency, aiming to modernize information dissemination and enhance engagement within institutions.(Sharma, 2020)

1.2 Problem statement

RP-Kigali College has difficulty communicating important information to the campus community, which can lead to miscommunication. The current notice boards are often outdated and do not allow for real-time interaction between students, staff, and instructors. This makes it hard for everyone to stay informed.

To solve these problems, we are developing a user friendly IoT-based smart notice board that will improve communication across the campus and make sharing information faster and more efficient.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to develop a smart notice board with a focus on enhancing the efficiency of communication in the campus of RP-Kigali College. This system aims to address the limitations of traditional paper notice boards which is outdated and not efficient in communicating.

1.4 Project objectives

1.4.1 General objectives

The main objective of the IoT Smart Notice Board project is to develop a digital way of displaying information in RP-Kigali College that enables remote sharing and display of notices, reminders, and announcements, thereby improving communication efficiency and building an informed community.

1.4.2 Specific objectives

- i. Provide an easy-to-use web-based system for RP-Kigali College campus notifications, reminders, and messages.
- ii. Establish an Internet of Things architecture that allows the user to know the usage of the display board.
- iii. To design and develop a prototype IoT-based smart notice board for information sharing.
- iv. Create a user-friendly online interface that makes it simple for authorized user to post and delete notices on the notice board.
- v. Integrate strong communication protocols between the web interface and the notice board to guarantee dependable and timely message delivery.

1.5 Research questions

- i. How can a web-based system be designed to simplify the posting, editing, and management of notifications, reminders, and messages for RP-Kigali College?
- ii. How is IoT architecture most effective for monitoring and reporting the usage of the smart notice board?
- iii. How are hardware and software required to design and prototype an IoT-based smart notice board that meets campus information sharing needs?
- iv. How can the user interface be optimized to make posting and editing messages simple and efficient for authorized users?
- v. What are the best communication protocols to ensure reliable, real-time message delivery between the web interface and the smart notice board?

1.6 Scope of the project

This study is geographically focused on RP-Kigali College, where the IoT-based smart notice board system will be implemented to enhance campus-wide communication. Theoretical boundaries cover the integration of IoT architecture, web-based interfaces, and reliable communication protocols for real-time information sharing. The study explores key issues such as usability, system performance, data transmission, and security in the context of smart campus systems. In terms of content, the research addresses the design and development of a user-friendly web-based platform, the monitoring of display usage, and the communication mechanisms between the notice board and the web interface, ensuring effective message delivery.

1.7 Methodology and Technics

- a) **Study area:** The project will be implemented in RP-Kigali College which is a major large communicating hub. This area was chosen because it needs an advanced technology to deliver notices and real time management of the notice board.

- b) **Study design:** Design will be employed for the development and testing of the IoT smart notice board. The study involved the construction of a notice board using Raspberry pi, Ultrasonic sensors, ESP8266 followed by rigorous testing and improvement processes.

- c) **Data collection methods:**
 - **Observation:** Observing people, especially users of notice boards, at specific times and locations to understand how traditional notice boards operate and their effectiveness. This will ensure that our project addresses the problem of information sharing effectively.
 - **Records and documents:** This technique is crucial for revisiting the history of the problem and finding effective solutions. Conducting recent documents done as final year projects to bring innovations to the project and learning their challenges while trying to overcome them.
 - **Focus groups:** Bringing together different groups of people to discuss issues related to information sharing and gather qualitative data on their reactions and suggestions.

d) Ethical considerations

- **Accountability:** The operators of the smart notice board should be accountable for the use of the system and the data collected. This means that they should be able to answer questions about how the system is used and what data is collected.
- **Security:** The smart notice board should be secure and prevent unauthorized access to the data. This is important to protect the privacy of individuals and organizations, as well as to prevent the system from being used for malicious purposes.

1.8 Delimitation

- The project will restrict content publishing to authorized user only.
- Will not explore advanced security features or complex networking configurations like Bluetooth or Zigbee.
- There are no plans for a large-scale deployment or the implementation of power backup solutions; instead, the project will install a single notice board in RP-Kigali College.

1.9 Organization of the project

The following is a proposed structure for a study on the development and implementation of a Smart notice board data monitoring via a web-based dashboard.

Conduct	Develop	Acquire	Build	Create	Integrate	Finalize	Perform
Conduct Raspberry pi research	Develop System Architecture	Acquire Components and materials	Build Hardware	Create Web-Based Dashboard	Integrate Hardware with Dashboard	Finalize System and Housing	Perform System Evaluation and Collect Feedback

Table 1 Organization of the project

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter contains information about some of the previous projects which are somehow related to this one of smart notice board. It also contains the names of the people who did these projects with the institutions they were working with, and the components they used.

2.1 Concepts, Opinions, Ideas from Authors/Experts

Most of the experts who worked on the projects related to the design and implementation of IoT based smart notice board, they did it with the intention of monitoring user-friendly interfaces significantly enhance system adoption and engagement, particularly in educational environments and also highlighting the role of strong communication protocols in ensuring reliable message delivery across IoT platforms.

2.2 Related study

Information board plays a vital role in displaying information in all educational institutions and most of the offices. Compared to the conventional type information display methods which are paper based with a digital information board, we can make sure that data/information passes to everyone(Kurian et al., 2021)

This innovative digital platform harnesses web-based technologies to establish a centralized and user-friendly system for the posting, management, and retrieval of announcements, notices, and updates. In the current era, there has been significant progress in information technology, and its widespread adoption is evident in almost every sector(Manchala et al., 2024)

Notice board is an essential information gathering system in our life. In our day-to-day life we can see notice boards in various places like, educational institutions, railway stations, shopping malls, Bus stations, offices etc. So, we can say that Notice boards are the places to leave public information such as advertise events, announce events or provide attention to the public, etc. Now-a-days a separate person is needed to stick the information on the notice board.(Penmetcha et al., 2020)

IoT-enabled digital noticeboard is user-friendly, cost-effective, highly visual, and easy to update. Whenever the university authorities pass a notice, it can be shown directly to the LCD monitor. There is no need to print the paper and attach it manually on the noticeboard. Many students do not have the habit of reading noticeboards. But by using the proposed system, we can get the attention of the students. As a result, many students will be able to know the important messages very easily.(Islam et al., 2022)

We choose the internet as a media to transfer information because of the popularity of the internet. The Internet of things (IoT) is a network of electronically embedded physical equipment, cars, home appliances and other goods. IOT allows us to establish connections and share the data between these objects.(Reddy, 2020)

In IOT based mostly internet Controlled bulletin board, web is used to wirelessly send the message from Browser to the show. a neighborhood internet server is made, this might be a worldwide server over internet. It gathers data from the cloud after switching on Raspberry pi. The site address for data collection from the cloud is already suggested by the processor software.(Journal et al., n.d.)

In the area of corporate communication, the modest notice board has long functioned as an important instrument for conveying information, sharing news, and encouraging community involvement. However, traditional paper-based and wired electronic notice boards have disadvantages, ranging from inefficiency to security flaws.(Paneru et al., 2024)

Effective communication within educational institutions is crucial for disseminating information to students and faculty members. Traditional notice boards are often limited in their reach and efficiency. To address this issue, a IOT based smart notice board is proposed.(Babu et al., n.d.)

In today's world of connectedness, people are becoming accustomed to easy access to information. Whether it's through the internet or television, people want to be informed and up-to-date with the latest events happening around the world (J. S. Lee 2007). Wired network connection such as Ethernet has many limitations depending on the need and type of connection. Now a day's people prefer wireless connection because they can interact with people easily and it require less time.(Parthiban, 2020)

Nonetheless, despite all the developments in telecommunications, there are still numerous circumstances when conventional forms of communication are favored. To reach broad audiences, community boards are still widely utilized in various institutions, including schools, workplaces, and public areas. Whether it's a reminder from the principal, a directive from the head of the company, or a warning about a potential risk, notice boards serve an important purpose in informing the community.(Salih et al., 2024)

A digital notice board, consisting of a unified display with LED panels, enhances the visibility of announcements and other essential information for the general public, students, and staff. To promote effective communication at both the internal and external levels, it is feasible to consistently exchange multimedia files such as documents, PDFs, videos, and photographs. Campus contact with students is being replaced by digital technology, rendering paper notice boards obsolete.(Ahil S. et al., 2024)

According to the all-related works above, we introduce our project designing and implementing an IoT based smart notice board to improve on the current used notice board in a college community. And then, in our project we also add a sensor on the notice board to detect the number of events on the notice board for the authorized user to know the people who accessed the notice board.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter provide details of the methods of data collection, the presentation format designed based on data collection instruments, and the techniques for data analysis. The interpretation of results derived from this comprehensive analysis sheds light on the effectiveness and reliability of the IoT smart notice board, serving as a bridge between implementation and meaningful findings.

3.1 Research design

The research design for this study is quasi-experimental, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods.

The quasi-experimental approach is appropriate because it allows for the development and testing of the IoT-based smart notice board system in a real-world setting without complete control over all variables. Quantitative data will be gathered by measuring the system's performance, including message delivery speed, uptime, and user interaction frequency, while qualitative data will be collected through surveys and interviews with users to assess the system's usability and effectiveness. This mixed-method approach provides a holistic understanding of the system's technical functionality and its impact on campus communication.

The combination of both approaches ensures that the study not only evaluates the system's operational efficiency but also its practical relevance and acceptance by users.

3.2 Research population

The research population includes students, staff, and administrators at RP-Kigali College who use the notice board system for campus updates. A sample will be taken from this group, focusing on those who regularly post or read messages. People who do not use the notice boards will not be included. The results will apply to the larger college community because they all share similar communication needs.

3.3 Sample size

To determine the sample size for this study, the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table is used, which provides recommended sample sizes based on population size. For an estimated population of 1000 students, staff, and administrators at RP Kigali College, a sample size of 278 is recommended. This ensures a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, making the results reliable and representative of the entire population. The sample size is sufficient for the study and supports the generalization of findings to the larger college community. This method is widely accepted for calculating sample sizes in social science research.

Sampling procedure

The stratified random sampling method will be used to ensure that all key groups (students, staff, and administrators) are represented in the sample. The population will first be divided into these groups, and then a random sample will be taken from each group to maintain proportionality. This approach ensures that the sample reflects the characteristics of the entire population and reduces sampling bias.

3.4 Research instrument

3.4.1 Choice of the research instrument

- **Observation:** This is a technique of gather a needed information where a data collector uses his or her eyes. Observing people, especially users of notice boards, at specific times and locations to understand how traditional notice boards operate and their effectiveness. This will ensure that our project addresses the problem of information sharing effectively.
- **Records and documents:** This technique is crucial for revisiting the history of the problem and finding effective solutions. Conducting recent documents done as final year projects to bring innovations to the project and learning their challenges while trying to overcome them.
- **Focus groups:** Bringing together different groups of people to discuss issues related to information sharing and gather qualitative data on their reactions and suggestions.

3.4.2 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the observation and focus group methods, experts will review them, and pilot observations will be conducted to confirm they gather the right information about user interactions with the IoT notice board. For reliability, a clear observation guide will be used to keep things consistent, and focus group discussions will be recorded and transcribed for further analysis. Using both methods together help with triangulation, making the findings more trustworthy.

3.5 Data gathering procedures

Below, it is shown the step-by-step procedure to gather the data from before, during and after the administration of the research instrument

1. Preparation Phase: Develop and review observation checklists and focus group guides, followed by pilot testing to refine the instruments.
2. Before Data Collection: Recruit participants, schedule sessions, and obtain consent to ensure ethical compliance.
3. During Data Collection: Conduct observations using the checklist to document interactions with the IoT notice board and facilitate focus group discussions, guiding participants and recording sessions.
4. After Data Collection: Transcribe focus group recordings and compile observational notes, analyze the data for key themes, and summarize the findings in a report.

3.6 Limitation of the study

- Power Backup: The system lacks a power backup, which could disrupt operations during outages and affect data collection reliability.
- Notification Indications: The system does not have indicators for new notifications, making it difficult for users to know when updates occur. This limitation may affect user engagement and interaction with the notice board.

CHAPTER FOUR: PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

This section provides a detail of the hardware and software design methodology, the algorithms, code implementation, and the testing and validation procedures. The goal of this chapter is to give detailed description of the process followed to build the system and provide a comprehensive understanding of the project's technical implementation.

4.1 Calculations

Our system encloses a number of calculations which are related to the working principle of the sensors. These calculations are performed by the microcontroller after the detection or triggering done by the sensors and the results are displayed on the screen.

Below it is shown the formula which ultrasonic sensor uses to detect the distance in which an obstacle is in: $\text{float distance} = (\text{duration} / 2.0) / 29.1$; (Calculate distance in cm).

4.2 Drawings

4.2.1 Block diagram of the project

Figure 1 Block diagram

4.2.2 Working principle of the project

Initially, the administrator uploads notices through a web interface on a PC (user'), where the notices are sent to and stored in a cloud database. The Raspberry Pi, connected to the internet via Wi-Fi, retrieves these notices from the cloud and displays them in real-time on a screen. An ultrasonic sensor attached to the NodeMCU detects the presence of users near the notice board. When a user is detected, the sensor sends data to the cloud database through the NodeMCU. This setup allows the administrator to monitor user engagement and can trigger specific actions, such as displaying event counts on the display. Overall, the system provides an effective, real-time, and interactive communication platform for the campus.

4.2.3 Flowchart

Figure 2Flowchart

This IoT-based Smart Notice Board for information sharing, the flow begins with an authorized user logging into a web dashboard to upload or update notices. The data is sent to a server, processed, and transmitted to a Raspberry Pi connected to a display screen. The notice is shown on the screen, while an ultrasonic sensor detects the number of people nearby. This data is stored in a database and reflected on the web dashboard, allowing the user to monitor interactions with the notice board. The system continuously updates and checks for new notices or viewer presence.

4.2.4 Circuit diagram

Figure 3Circuit diagram

In the IoT-based Smart Notice Board, the circuit diagram connects an ultrasonic sensor to the NodeMCU for detecting nearby viewers. The ultrasonic sensor has four main pins: VCC, GND, TRIG, and ECHO. The VCC is connected to the Vin pin of the NodeMCU, while GND goes to a ground pin. The TRIG pin is connected to D1, and the ECHO pin is connected to D2).

The Raspberry Pi also connects to the TV screen via HDMI to display the notices uploaded from the web dashboard, while the sensor's readings are processed to monitor the number of viewers near the board.

4.3 Specifications

4.3.1 Main components Used

i. ESP8266 NodeMCU

The ESP8266 NodeMCU is versatile and widely used Wi-Fi module based on the ESP8266 microcontroller. It is employed in IoT projects for its capability to connect to Wi-Fi networks and facilities communication with other devices over the internet

The ESP8266 NodeMCU operates by running code to connect to Wi-Fi network and execute various tasks. It can interface with sensors, collect data and send /receive data packets over the internet. ESP8266 Node MCU operates at 3.3 volts and support Wi-Fi connectivity, meeting our project's communication requirements functionality interface with sensors, collect data, send /receive data packets over the internet.(Firmansyah et al., 2020)

Figure 4NodeMCU

Role in this project: In the IoT-based smart notice board project at RP KIGALI COLLEGE, the NodeMCU connects the ultrasonic sensor to Wi-Fi. It allows users to view the sensor's data on a web dashboard. The NodeMCU also communicates with sensors to track how many people are viewing the notice board and sends this data to the database. It controls the display of the notices on the board and updates it when new information is uploaded.

ii. Ultrasonic sensor

An ultrasonic sensor measures distance using high-frequency sound waves. It emits an ultrasonic wave, detects its reflection from an object, and calculates the distance based on the travel time. Key components include a transmitter, receiver, and control circuit. Common applications are in distance measurement, obstacle detection, level sensing, and proximity sensing. Advantages include non-contact measurement, versatility in different environments, and accuracy. Limitations include potential interference from environmental factors like temperature and humidity. (Park et al., 2010)

Figure 5 Ultrasonic

Ultrasonic sensors are used to detect people near the notice board. They sense when someone is within 1 meter of the board and count how many people come to view the notices. This information is sent to the system, so it can keep track of how many people look at the board.

iii. Connecting wires

An electrical wire is the electro technical component used to transport electricity to transmit energy and information. It is made of a conductive material, single or multiple strands, often surrounded by an insulating envelope. The inside of the electrical wire is called the “core”.

Wire in this project will be used in creating connections between different components used. Electric charge from the source will pass through the wires on the board. (Dolgopolova et al., 2019)

Figure 6 Jumper wires

These connecting wires will be used to transfer power and information from one component to another.

iv. Printed circuit board (PCB)

Printed circuit boards are boards used as the base in most electronics- both as a physical support piece and as the wiring areas for the surface-mounted and socketed components. PCBs are most common made out of fiberglass, composite epoxy, or another composite material.(Rabinovich & Epstein, n.d.)

Figure 7PCB

In this project PCB is used for connecting together different component.

v. Raspberry Pi

The Raspberry Pi is a compact, cost-effective single-board computer designed for versatility and educational purposes. It features various input and output options, including Wi-Fi connectivity, making it ideal for IoT projects. Its ability to run multiple operating systems and software applications allows for extensive customization.(Upton & Halfacree, 2013)

Figure 8 Raspberry Pi 4b

Role in the Project: In this project, the Raspberry Pi 4b serves as the main receiver, retrieving real-time notices from a cloud database and displaying them on a connected TV screen. It facilitates user interaction by processing data from the ultrasonic sensor, enhancing communication and engagement on campus

4.4 Cost estimation

4.4.1 Project plan

Table 2 Cost Estimation

S/N	Task to	Start Date	Target	Amount	Remarks
1	Conduct research and gather requirements	05/04/2024	25/04/2024	7,000	Completed
2	Develop system architecture and design	30/04/2024	01/05/2024	5,000	Completed
3	Preparing project proposal and documentation	02/05/2024	25/06/2024	17,000	Completed

4	Pre-defense	28/06/2024	28/06/2024	N/A	Completed
5	Purchase and obtain hardware components	08/07/2024	10/07/2024	30,500	Completed
6	Design and develop the hardware system	11/07/2024	21/07/2024	6,000	Completed
7	Develop the web dashboard and database	01/08/2024	19/09/2024	4,000	Completed
8	Integrate the web platform with the hardware	20/09/2024	09/10/2024	2,000	Completed
9	Finalize the system and hardware housing	10/10/2024	11/10/2024	19,000	Completed
10	Final testing and evaluation	14/10/2024	15/10/2024	4,000	Completed
11	Prepare project documentation and final report	16/10/2024	17/10/2024	12,000	Completed
12	TOTAL			106,500	

4.5 Implementation

4.5.1 Log in page

The login form is titled "Login". It features two input fields: the first contains the text "Admin" and the second contains three dots "...". Below these fields is a prominent blue "Login" button. Underneath the "Login" button is a smaller, light blue "Signup" link.

Figure 9 Log in Page

4.5.2 Dashboard

The dashboard header includes "Smart Notice Board" on the left, "Add New User" in a blue button in the center, and "Logout" in a red button on the right. The main content area starts with "Welcome, Admin" in a large font. Below this are three sections: "Upload a New File" with a file selection field and an "Upload" button; "Add Text Content" with a text input field and an "Add Text" button; and "Your Files and Text Content" which shows a list item with the text "Hello", a count of "0", and two action buttons: "Delete" (red) and "Select for Display" (green).

Figure 10 Dashboard

4.5.3 Notice database

Figure 11 Database

4.5.4 Sensor database

Figure 12 Sensor Database

This web dashboard serves as the central interface for the use to interact with the system. It allows the user to securely log in and submit notices, including text, images, and documents, which are then stored in the database and displayed on the campus smart notice board. The dashboard also enables the user to manage their submissions, providing features to upload, or delete notices as needed. This interface ensures that the process of sharing information is user-friendly and efficient, with real-time updates.

Additionally, the web dashboard offers monitoring and data visualization functionalities. It displays the number of people detected who read the notice using ultrasonic sensor and records them in the database. This data is then stored and displayed on the dashboard, giving user insights into engagement levels. The combination of submission, management and views detection enhances the system's effectiveness, making it a dynamic tool for information distribution and feedback.

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter marks the end of this report. It contains an executive summary for the working principle and the way to use this system and the recommendation for the future work. Where we invite anyone who would be interested in this project to add some new features that were not able to work on.

5.1 Conclusion

The project successfully created an IoT-based system that streamlined campus communication by providing an easy-to-use web platform for uploading and displaying notifications in real time. It also incorporated an ultrasonic sensor to monitor user interactions with the notice board, enabling administrators to track its usage. The Raspberry Pi efficiently retrieved notices from the database, demonstrating the system's capability to enhance communication and engagement on campus. Overall, the project achieved its objectives and proved the feasibility of the smart notice board system.

5.2 Recommendations

We recommend RP-Kigali College to use this project as it will improve its communication within the campus.

We also recommend other RP Colleges and other places where easy communication with large number of people is required like hospitals, schools, airports and local government institutions offices (Sectors, districts).

5.3 Suggestion for further study

For further studies, we suggest:

1. **Integration of Advanced Sensors:** Future research could explore the use of additional sensors, such as facial recognition or RFID technology, to enhance user interaction and tailor content based on the specific audience. This could make the system more adaptive and personalized.
2. **Security Improvements:** To safeguard the integrity of the system, security measures should be strengthened. This includes implementing secure login protocols for administrators and encrypting data transmission between the web interface and the display system to prevent unauthorized access.
3. **Notification Indicator Enhancement:** The absence of a clear indication for new notifications was identified as a limitation. It is recommended to implement a visual or auditory alert system to notify users when a new notice is posted or when an existing notice has been updated. This feature would increase user interaction and engagement with the system.
4. **Power Optimization Strategies:** Further research is recommended on optimizing the power consumption of the system, particularly with the ESP8266 and display units. This could include energy-efficient designs or the use of solar power to make the system more sustainable.
5. **Development of Mobile Application:** A study could be conducted on developing a complementary mobile application that allows users to receive notifications directly on their smartphones. This would enhance the accessibility of the system and provide an alternative way to engage with the notices.

REFERENCES

- Ahil S., Viswa R.L, Rarojin S., & Evanjalina A.B. (2024). Smart Wireless Message Display: Enhancing Communication with Intelligent Technology. *Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research*, 08(02), 94–101. <https://doi.org/10.46759/ijrsr.2024.8211>
- Babu, T. V. A., Tharuni, M., Ganesh, T., Hareesh, M., & Yogesh, P. (n.d.). *Smart Notice Board using Voice Chat*. 269–283.
- Dolgoplova, E. A., Galitskiy, V. A., Martin, C. R., Gregory, H. N., Yarbrough, B. J., Rice, A. M., Berseneva, A. A., Ejegbavwo, O. A., Stephenson, K. S., Kittikhunnatham, P., Karakalos, S. G., Smith, M. D., Greytak, A. B., Garashchuk, S., & Shustova, N. B. (2019). *Connecting Wires: Photoinduced Electronic Structure Modulation in Metal – Organic Frameworks*. 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.8b13853>
- Firmansyah, R., Yusuf, M., Saputra, P. P. S., Prasetyo, M. E., Mochtar, F. M., & Kurniawan, F. A. (2020). *IoT Based Temperature Control System Using Node MCU ESP 8266*. 196(Ijcse), 401–407.
- Islam, S., Ali, M. L., & Sadi, M. S. (2022). Development of an IoT-Enabled Digital Noticeboard. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, 437(November), 479–492. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-2445-3_33
- Journal, I., Multidisciplinary, O. F., & Journal, P. R. (n.d.). *WIRELESS NOTICE BOARD USING IOT Aastha Miten, Bolbam Kumar Yadav, Abhishek Kumar Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering IIMT College of Engineering, Greater Noida, UP, India*. 4(6), 33–41.
- Kurian, N. S., Hemanth Kumar, R. K., Abinaya Shree, M., & Esakkiammal, S. (2021). IoT based Wireless Notice Board Using Raspberry Pi. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1979(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1979/1/012058>
- Manchala, M., Pramod Reddy, K., Manasa, P., Ankush Reddy, S., & Sangameshwar, U. (2024). KGR CET Notice Board. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 392, 01093. <https://doi.org/10.1051/matecconf/202439201093>
- Paneru, B., Paneru, B., Poudyal, R., Shah, K. B. B., & Poudyal, K. N. (2024). A Low-Cost

- Prototype for Edge-Computing Powered Smart Display Board. *International Journal of Informatics, Information System and Computer Engineering (INJIISCOM)*, 5(2), 192–205.
<https://doi.org/10.34010/injiiscom.v5i2.12508>
- Park, J., Je, Y., Lee, H., & Moon, W. (2010). *Design of an ultrasonic sensor for measuring distance and detecting obstacles*. 50, 340–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultras.2009.10.013>
- Parthiban, K. G. (2020). *Wireless Notice Board with Wide Range Communication*. 7(7), 96–100.
- Penmetcha, K., Andey, S., Mudunuri, S., Prudhvi, D. S., Pericharla, V., Ramavath, A. K., & Kapula, P. R. (2020). (PDF) Smart Notice Board. *Electronics and Communication Engineering, October*. <https://doi.org/10.9790/2834-1502022327>
- Rabinovich, O., & Epstein, A. (n.d.). *Analytical Design of Printed-Circuit-Board (PCB) Metagratings for Perfect Anomalous Reflection*. 1–10.
- Reddy, K. (2020). *Web controlled notice board*. 8(4), 4202–4207.
- Salih, M. M., Ahmed, W. S., Hamdoun, S. H., & Shalenko, V. (2024). Displaying a Message on the Notice Board Using a PC. *Conference of Open Innovation Association, FRUCT*, 642–651.
<https://doi.org/10.23919/fruct61870.2024.10516386>
- Sharma. (2020). No Title. In *web based smart notice board*.
- Upton, E., & Halfacree, G. (2013). *Raspberry Pi User Guide , 2nd Edition. December*.

APPENDIX

The ultrasonic sensor is used to detect the number of people who read the notice board.

Figure 13 Sensor circuit

NOTICE BOARD DISPLAY

Figure 14 notice display

CODE

```
1  #include <ArduinoJson.h>
2  #include <ESP8266HTTPClient.h>
3  #include <ESP8266Wifi.h>
4  #include <WiFiClient.h>
5  #include <WiFiClientSecureBearSSL.h>
6
7  #define TRIG D1
8  #define ECHO D2
9  #define DISTANCE_TRESH 50
10
11 const char* ssid = "RREAL EMMY";
12 const char* password = "12345678900";
13
14 void setup() {
15     Serial.begin(115200);
16     WiFi.mode(WIFI_STA);
17     WiFi.begin(ssid, password);
18
19     // Wait for connection with a timeout
20     int wifi_attempts = 0;
21     while (WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED && wifi_attempts < 20) {
22         delay(1000);
23         Serial.print("Connecting...");
24         wifi_attempts++;
25     }
26
27     if (WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED) {
28         Serial.println("Failed to connect to WiFi.");
29     } else {
30         Serial.println("Connected to WiFi.");
31     }
32
33     pinMode(TRIG, OUTPUT);
```

```

34   pinMode(ECHO, INPUT);
35 }
36
37 void loop() {
38   long distance = measureDistance();
39   Serial.println(distance);
40
41   int count = 0;
42   while (distance < DISTANCE_TRESH) {
43     Serial.println("User detected");
44     distance = measureDistance();
45     count++;
46     if(distance>DISTANCE_TRESH&&count>=10){
47       Serial.println("User left");
48       sendCount();
49     }else if(distance>DISTANCE_TRESH&&count<10){
50       Serial.println("User left");
51     }
52     delay(1000);
53   }
54
55 }
56
57 void sendCount() {
58   if (WiFi.status() == WL_CONNECTED) {
59     std::unique_ptr<BearSSL::WiFiClientSecure>client(new BearSSL::WiFiClientSecure);
60     client ->setInsecure();//Ignore SSL cert validation
61
62
63     HTTPClient https;
64
65     // Begin with the WiFiClient and URL
66     https.begin(*client, "https://noticeboard24.onrender.com/count");

```

```

67     https.addHeader("Content-Type", "application/json");
68
69     int httpCode = https.POST(""); // Send an empty POST request
70
71     Serial.println("Sending POST request");
72     if (httpCode > 0) {
73         Serial.println(httpCode); // Print HTTP response code
74         String payload = https.getString();
75         Serial.println(payload); // Print server response
76     } else {
77         Serial.print("Error on sending POST: ");
78         Serial.println(httpCode);
79     }
80     https.end(); // Close connection
81 }
82 }
83
84
85 long measureDistance() {
86     digitalWrite(TRIG, LOW);
87     delayMicroseconds(2);
88     digitalWrite(TRIG, HIGH);
89     delayMicroseconds(10);
90     digitalWrite(TRIG, LOW);
91
92     long duration = pulseIn(ECHO, HIGH);
93     long distance = duration * 0.034 / 2;
94     return distance;
95 }

```

Figure 15 Arduino IDE Code